

Electronic Voting Using Blockchain

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Abstract: online voting is achieving momentum in modern society. It has splendid potential to decrease organizational prices and growth voter turnout. It gets rid of the need to print poll papers or open polling stations, citizens can vote from wherever there is a web connection. Online voting solutions, on the other hand, are viewed with caution since they constitute a new threat. Electronic voting mechanisms must be legitimate, accurate, safe and convenient since a single flaw will be able to create a massive vote tampering. Adoption may be hampered by possible issues with processes. blockchain technology is introduced to beat those problems; it provides decentralized nodes for electronic voting and is used to dispense electronic voting structures particularly because of their end to end verification assistance. This technology possessing distribution, non-repudiation and protection characteristics is a quality alternative for usual digital voting solutions. The intention of this paper is to look over its associated trouble in future advancements and the block chain based voting research and online voting system status quo. This study provides a conceptual description of the intended blockchain-based totally digital vote casting utility and an introduction to the blockchain's basic structure and properties in relation to digital balloting. As a result of the research, it was identified that blockchain structures can also help to resolve some of the challenges of ongoing election systems. The most frequently reported issues with blockchain packaging on the other hand are privacy, security and transaction speed. The safety of remote participation should be attainable and transaction speed must be addressed in a viable blockchain based complete electronic balloting complex. Because of these issues, it was determined that current architecture truly needed when they would be deployed in voting systems.

Keywords: Voting, Electronic-Voting, Blockchain, Scalability

I. INTRODUCTION

Not only for democratic countries, but also for state voter's acceptance and accountability, electoral integrity is crucial. From a government outlook, electronic voting mechanisms can escalate voter participation and confidence; furthermore, it revives interest in the voting device. It is essential to assure that voter confidence does not diminish. Engineers across the globe have developed advanced voting techniques that furnish some anti-corruption protection while also ensuring that the voting process is accurate. Technology delivered the brand new electronic voting techniques and techniques,

which are vital. Digital balloting election trust while in comparison to traditional balloting. For online or electronic voting, Blockchain technology gives a decentralized node.. Blockchain is an attractive alternative to traditional electronic voting systems with functions including decentralization, non-repudiation, and security protection. block chain is brought into play to shape a temper proof vote casting process. It is a chain of blocks linked with the help of hash which is estimated from previous block. A blockchain architecture for handling the voting process is presented. It is a three step method comprising Registration setup, balloting and vote end result calculation.

II. HOW DOES A BLOCKCHAIN WORKS

A blockchain is a distributed database that is shared across computer network nodes. It's a storage that carry data in an electronic form. A P2P network used to create a chain of blocks called a blockchain. A hash and timestamp are introduced to the preceding block in every block on the blockchain. The entire written data is divided into blocks,

each of which includes a portion of the preceding block's complete contents as part of its own. If a piece of code is altered, the block's hash containing it must be computed, as must all subsequently hashes. Blockchain enables immutability as a result of this feature. If an attacker tries to tamper with the data, he intends to modify the values of all the blocks. hashes at same which is impossible.

III. ARCHITECTURAL COMPONENTS OF BLOCKCHAIN

- Node — A computer in the blockchain architecture
- Transaction — A blockchain contributor-tested data record that acts as a near-immutable validation of a monetary transaction or agreement's legitimacy.
- Block — A sealed facts container containing: hash code, previous block hash code, and ,transactions.
- Chain — A set of blocks in a specific order.
- Miners — Are the validators.
- Consensus — A set of rules and agreements that govern the use of blockchain technology

IV. KEY TRAITS OF BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

- Cryptography — Due to sophisticated computations and cryptographic evidence among the participants, blockchain transactions are transparent and simple.
- Immutability — A blockchain's data cannot be modified or destroyed.
- Provenance — Every transaction in the blockchain ledger can track back to start.
- Decentralization — The complete distributed database is available to all. A consensus set of rules is responsible for network control, unlike with a centralized device.
- Anonymity — Each member of the blockchain community has a randomly created address, rather than a real name. This protects users' anonymity, which is particularly important in a public blockchain.
- Transparency — The blockchain machine will not be damaged since it takes a significant amount of computer power to completely recreate the blockchain network.

V. E-VOTING USING BLOCKCHAIN

- Blockchain technology offers a decentralized node for online voting or electronic voting.
- Blockchain is an attractive opportunity to traditional electronic balloting systems with functions inclusive of decentralization, non-repudiation, and security.

- Voting is a new phase of blockchain technology in this place, the researchers are seeking to leverage advantages which includes transparency, secrecy, and nonrepudiation which are vital for balloting applications.
- A digital ballot box of this type enables individual voting secrecy to be ensured through encryption. All outcomes may be confirmed using cryptographic proof at the same time.

Voting block

VI. MAJOR LIMITATION IN USING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Worlds first blockchain supported elections just happened in Sierra Leone gone wrong. Why? Scalability is a major concern Blockchain technology. For a couple of users, blockchain works well. When the network is utilized for large-scale elections, however, the number of consumers increases, resulting in a lower charge and a shorter time to complete the transaction. The use of the expanding number of nodes in the blockchain community exacerbates scalability concerns. The device's scalability is already a major issue in the current election situation. As a result, latency will grow, which will have an impact on security. This study proposes a solution to the problem.

Framework	Year Release	Generation Time	Hash Rate	Transactions Per Sec	Cryptographic Algorithm	Mining Difficulty	Power Consumption	Reward/Block	Scalability
Bitcoin	2008	9.7 min	899.624 This	4.6 max 7	ECDSA	High (around 165,498,935,118)	Very High	25 BTC	Very Low
Ethereum	2015	10 to 19 s	198.59 This	15	ECDSA	High (around 10,382,182)	High	5 ether	Low
Hyperledger Fabric	2015	10 ms	NA	3500	ECC	No mining required	Very Low	No built-in cryptocurrency	Good
Litecoin	2011	2.5 min	1,307 This	56	Scrypt	Low 55,067	Moderate	25 LTC	Moderate
Ripple	2012	3.5 s	NA	1500	RPCA	No mining required	Very Low	Base Fee	Good
Dogecoin	2013	1 min	1.4 This	33	Scrypt	Low 21,482	Low	10,000 Doge	Low
Peercoin	2012	10 min	693,090 This	8	Hybrid	Moderate (476,580,083)	Low	67.12 PPC	Low

VII. SOLUTION

Sharding: Sharding is a method of parallelizing blockchains in order to improve their scale. To allow for high concurrency in data, the data should be horizontally partitioned into pieces, each known as a shard database partitioning strategy used by blockchain companies for scalability, allowing them to process more transactions per second. Sharding divides a whole network into smaller barriers called as Shards Every shard has its own statistics, which distinguishes it from other shards and makes it unique and unbiased. Because it divides a blockchain community into independent shards, sharding can help reduce network latency or slowness. Sharding spreads out a blockchain's load.

VIII. HORIZONTAL PARTITIONING

- performed by dividing databases into rows and horizontally separating them.
- Shards, as the rows are known, are created entirely based on qualities.
- Each shard may still be shared with the opposite shards, preserving a core feature of the blockchain era: the decentralised record.
- provides for faster data transactions because when information is dispersed across several databases, each smaller database may process certain statistics at the same time as the others.
- As a result, the more shards you have, the more data you can process in parallel.

IX. CONCLUSION

The objective of this research is to analyze and compare contemporary investigations on blockchain based digital

balloting system and to come up with solutions for the shortcoming scalability. The blockchain's potential is vital to furnish digital voting, newfangled solutions for blockchain based electronic balloting and plausible research paths o blockchain based digital balloting system. Moreover, every single citizen and independent observer might see the voting data stored in those advised systems. Then again, researchers observed that most courses on blockchain-based totally electronic voting identified and addressed similar troubles. There have been many look at gaps in electronic balloting that want to be addressed in future research. loss of transparency, reliance on untrustworthy structures, and resistance to compulsion are all capability drawbacks that ought to be addressed. As further analysis is needed, we aren't entirely aware of all of the risks related with the safety and scalability of blockchain-based totally electronic balloting systems. Adopting blockchain balloting techniques may additionally divulge users to unexpected security risks and flaws. Blockchain technologies require a greater state-of-the-art software architecture in addition to managerial knowledge. For a couple of customers, blockchain operates well. Still and all, whilst the community is utilized for massive-scale elections, the quantity of users increases, ensuing in a higher price and time intake for ingesting the transaction. There is just one approach to increase scalability: parallelize the processes. Implementing sharding is the approach proposed in this study to address the issue of scalability. The statistics should be horizontally partitioned into parts known as shards in order to allow high concurrency in records. The Scalability problem must be solved utilizing the supplied solution, according to the findings of this research. Sharding

X . REFERENCE

1. Liu, Y.; Wang, Q. An E-voting Protocol Based on Blockchain. *IACR Cryptol. Eprint Arch.* 2017, 2017, 1043
2. Shahzad, B.; Crowcroft, J. Trustworthy Electronic Voting Using Adjusted Blockchain Technology. *IEEE Access* 2019, 7, 24477–24488.
3. Racsko, P. Blockchain and Democracy. *Soc. Econ.* 2019, 41, 353–369.
4. Yaga, D.; Mell, P.; Roby, N.; Scarfone, K. Blockchain technology overview. *arXiv* 2019, arXiv:1906.11078